

Factors Influencing Dividend Policy: Evidence from Electricity Sector of Pakistan

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Abstract:

One of the important decisions the company is to decide about the company's dividend policy. The main purpose of paying a dividend is that companies want to attract more investors, satisfy existing once and maintaining a good reputation. In Pakistan there are different sectors and there are different factors that influence their dividend policy. This study has used a few factors of them such as tax, liquidity, profitability, market to book value, debt to equity and cash flow. The result of the study states that liquidity, profitability, market to book value and cash flow have a significant impact on the dividend policy of the electricity producing companies. Whereas debt to equity and tax does not have a significant impact on the dividend policy of the company. Results also state that cash flow, debt to equity, tax and MV to BV have a positive relationship with the dividend policy of companies. The factors such as profitability and liquidity have a negative relationship with the dividend policy of firms in Pakistan.

Keywords: Dividend Policy, Electricity Sector of Pakistan

Introduction

The word dividend is derived from the word "dividendum". Dividendum means things to be divided. The general definition of dividend is the amount of money that is paid annually to its owners (shareholders) by the company from its profit (Wikipedia). Dividend policy is policy or decision of a company to pay, not to pay or how much it should pay from its profit or reserves, the dividend to shareholders. Dividend policy always remains a very important issue for investors, firms and researchers. Investors and firms rate positively to an organization that pays a dividend. Dividends provide information about the future performance of the company. The decrease or not paying a dividend is a signal to the market that the company is retaining cash flows for future investment or the firm is uncertain about its future earning and thus not paying dividends. (Mudassir 2014).

In finance about dividend policy there are 2 major opinions. Firstly, Miller and Modigliani (1961) and its followers considered that dividend policy is unrelated and has no effect on the capital's cost price of firms as well as on the stock's price of firms. Miller and Modigliani (1958) show that the value of a firm is free from dividend policy. They believed that investors do not worry about the dividend policy of a company for the reason that investors can buy shares

and borrow for them. So in the presence of taxes or bankruptcy costs, dividend policy becomes unrelated.

The second opinion is of James E Walter and Gordon (1963) and considered dividend policy relevant. According to Walter's model dividends are relevant and affect the share price of the firms. Besides this investment policy of a firm is also linked with the dividend policy of the firm because the decision of firms to pay or not to pay dividends depends on whether the firm has enough opportunity to invest the retained earnings.

Most researchers have examined the impact of dividend policy on stock prices. Some researchers argue that dividend policy affects the stock price while some argue it not. This study

basically tries to examine the dividend policy of electricity companies in Pakistan.

This study focuses on identifying the factors that determine the dividend policy of the companies. There are different factors that are responsible for the dividend payment of a company. This study has used a few factors of them such as tax, liquidity, profitability, market to book value, debt to equity and cash flow. These factors have been used based on different theories and research papers. These variables are already used in different research papers but in different sectors. Different businesses have different natures such as manufacturing or services, trading etc. on the base of different natures of business, it is also possible that the dividend policy of different sectors is affected by different factors.

1.1 Power Generation and Distribution Sector in Pakistan

In Pakistan electricity is generated by both private firms as well as government firms. Electricity is transmitted, distributed and retail supplied by the two, coordinating with separate public firms; i.e. WAPDA (Water and Power Development Authority) and K-Electric (Karachi Electric). WAPDA is transmitting and distributing the electricity in all over Pakistan except Karachi and K-Electric is transmitting the electricity in Karachi and its surrounding areas (Wikipedia The Free Encyclopedia 2016). There are different reasons for the shortfall of electricity in Pakistan such as aging of the equipment, wastage of energy, high cost of fuel, distribution system etc. In the power generation and distribution sector some firms are owned by the government while there are private owners also. The key feature of the Electricity industry is that they are subject to a specific sector and policies of this sector do not apply to other regulated industries such as Banking and Insurance Industry (Carlo, Laura and Klaus 2013). According to Carlo and Klaus (2013) the policies which are followed by the Electricity industry are different from other sectors. Therefore, this study has taken eight electricity companies to examine the dividend policy of the electricity sector of Pakistan. For this study following eight

different electricity producing companies are taken as a sample.

- 1) Genertech Pakistan Limited
- 2) Ideal Energy Limited
- 3) Kohinoor Energy Limited
- 4) KAPCO
- 5) Sitara Energy Limited.
- 6) The Hub Power Company Limited
- 7) Nishat Power Limited
- 8) Kohinoor Power Company Limited

1.2. Problem Statement:

In Pakistan there are many firms which are paying a dividend. Similarly, there are also many companies which are not paying a dividend. So firstly, a study has to identify the dividend paying electricity companies. Moreover, the question arises that what are the factors that influence the company to pay a dividend. In Pakistan the electricity sector has not gained much focused as other sectors. In different commercial sectors there are different factors that play a key role in determining their policy. Cash flow, debt to equity, MV to BV ratio, liquidity, profitability, and tax are key factors that play a very vital role in the policy making of any company. The study has tried to identify the factors that influence the dividend policy of an electricity company in Pakistan.

1.3. Significance:

The study is beneficial for the investor, board of directors, new researchers and literature.

- 1) Normally investors try to invest in those companies which pay a dividend because they want to get the share out of profit. Therefore, this study will help the investors to make their best decision and it will identify those factors on the basis of which investors can make their decisions.
- 2) The study will be beneficial for the board of directors of a company. The main objective of any organization is normally the maximization of profit and shareholders' satisfaction. This study will help the board of directors in making their decision regarding companies' profit maximization and shareholders, satisfaction.
- 3) Moreover, the study is an addition to existing literature and identifying avenues for further research in this area.

1.4. Research Question:

- 1) What are the determinants of dividend policy of electricity producing companies?
- 2) Is there any impact of liquidity, profitability, tax, MV to BV, debt to equity and cash flows on dividend policy of electricity producing companies in Pakistan?

1.5. Objectives:

The objective of the study is as follows.

- 1) The objective of the study is to identify those electricity companies which are paying a dividend.
- 2) What are the determinants of dividend policy of electricity producing companies?
- 3) To identify the impact of dividend policy determinants i.e. liquidity, profitability, tax, MV to BV, debt to equity, and cash flows on dividend policy of electricity producing companies in Pakistan?

LITERATURE REVIEW

There is an ample literature available to analyze the impact of different factors on the dividend policy of different companies. In following there is a brief review of the literature.

Carlo, Laura and Klaus (2013), In their study tries to examine the reciprocal action between regulation and structure of ownership and their effects on the dividend payout decisions. They took 106 listed companies in the electricity sector from 17 European countries. In their study they used the modified Classical Lintner (1956)'s model. They examined the smoothing of a dividend of the company by checking regulatory regimes which were incentive vs non-incentive or in other words cost based and governance regimes such as private control vs state control of the firm. The results of the study state that on the basis of incentive regulation firms smooth their dividend less and they are always ready to change their dividend payment with changing profit whereas cost based regulation firms have a smooth dividend. The lower smoothing of dividend incases incentive regulation is possible if firms are private. Contrast to that, state-controlled firms continue to smooth their dividends and to pay larger dividends, despite moving from cost-based to incentive regulation

Klaus Gurgler (2013), this study was conducted in Austria in the banking sector for the period from 1991 to 1999. The study basically tried to examine the relationship between dividend policy and corporate governance. The study raised the question of why firms did not cut the dividends when required and pay the dividend when it should be. The study argued that cooperate governance can be examined to found out the answers to these questions. The study concluded that state-controlled firms had a smooth dividend and these firms mostly unwilling to cut the dividend. The private firms or in other words family firms had less smooth dividends and these forms less reluctant to cut the dividend.

Mehdi, Salehi and Shahnaz (2010), conducted this study in Iran. They used the data of all listed companies of the Tehran stock exchange of 9 years from 2000 to 2008. They used the regression analysis for the statistical tests and for processing their information SPSS software was used. They raised the question that is there any relationship between dividend policy and profitability, beta rate, retained earnings, P/E and debt ratio. The empirical findings of the study stated that there is a significant relationship between the size of a specific firm and retained earnings of the firm whereas a direct relationship exists between the profitability of a firm and its dividend

policy. The study also concludes that above these factors have a negative relation with the debt ratio, beta rate and P/E of the firm.

Dr. Bahaa Awad (2015), conducted a study on fifty-six (56) companies of different sectors that were listed on the Kuwait Stock Exchange during the period between 2011 to 2014. The secondary data was used in the study. OLS technique was used for the analysis purpose. The study examined the impact of size, leverage and profitability on dividend payout policy of the firm which was listed on the Kuwait stock exchange. The study concluded that the dividend policy of the firms listed on the Kuwait Stock Market is positively affected by the firm's size, profitability and leverage. The study also stated that these determinants of dividend policy of the developed countries could be applied for the countries which were developing.

Franklin and Muthusamy (2010), conducted a study on the determinants of dividend policy of the Indian paper industry. The study was conducted on the top ten firms of the Indian paper industry which were listed on the Bombay stock exchange. Their study had used the secondary data which were collected from the Center for Monitoring Indian Company. The Lintner dividend model was used for the analysis purpose. EPS, market to book value, liquidity, price earnings ratio were the important independent variables of the study. The study finds the negative impact of leverage and EPS on the dividend payout of the firm.

Eliasu Nuhu (2014), conducted the study in Ghana on 30 listed companies for the period from 2000 to 2009. The paper basically tries to identify those factors that influence the dividend policy of the firms in Ghana. OLS (ordinary least square) technique was used for that purpose. The study had used secondary data for the analysis purpose. The empirical finding states that in Ghana the noticeable determinants of dividend policy are board size, board independence, the square of profitability and leverage. The results of that study were accurate with the agency theory. The results of the study were consistent with the tax effect hypothesis as well as accurate with the signaling theory.

Narman Kuzucu (2015), conducted the study in Turkey to investigate those factors that influence the decision of the dividend of the firm. The study used panel data of eight years from 2006 to 2013. The study used secondary data from non-financial firms. The study used the fixed effects model and pooled OLS regression model for the analysis purpose. The study states that private firms, profitability, and leverage have a negative impact on the dividend of a firm whereas the size is positively related to the dividend policy of the firm. The study also showed that the maturity hypothesis of Grullon, Michaely and Swaminathan (2002) which assumes that with the passage of time earnings of a firm decrease due to which investment opportunities also decrease which leads firm towards dividend payout to shareholders.

Ali Tariq (2015), conducted this study on different firms of Pakistan and India. The firms were randomly selected from different sectors except banking and financial sector. The

study used Multiple regression techniques and data for the period from 2010 to 2014. The study basically tries to identify the determinants of payout ratio and leverage in India and Pakistan jointly. The variables of the study were ownership structure, liquidity, profitability and firm size. The study concludes that the size of a firm has a positive impact on the leverage of the firm. Besides all other variables have a negative impact on the leverage of a firm. The result of the second regression states that all variables positively affect the payout ratio of the firm except liquidity and profitability.

Christopher and Khoury (2014), conducted a study in Lebanon at Lebanese banks listed on the Beirut stock exchange. The study used the two different techniques such as OLS and dynamic panel regression for analyzing seven different variables and their impact on the dividend ratios. The study used secondary data for the analysis purpose to acquire the desired results. The variables of the study were leverage, firm size, growth, firm risk, previous year's dividend payout, profitability, liquidity, and current dividend payout ratio. The empirical finding states that Lebanese banks' size, risk and last dividend has a positive impact on their payout ratios but profitability and growth have a negative impact. The study also concludes that the bank prefers investing in earning than paying a dividend.

Robert King (2015), conducted research on thirty (30) non-financial and non-utility companies in Kenya for a period of five (5) years from 2008 to 2012. The study used the Tobit Regression model and 6 factors to identify the determinants of the dividend payout ratios. The factors which were used to examine the dividend payout ratio of these non-financial and non-utility companies were earnings, firm size, growth opportunities, retained earnings to total assets ratio, leverage and market to book ratio. The study concluded that debt ratio, firm size and growth rate have a negative impact on the payout ratio whereas the other three factors such as retained earnings, earnings and market to book ratios have a positive impact on the payout of the firms.

Intikhab Alam (2007), conducted research on the banking sector of Pakistan. He used the data from seven different years from 2001 to 2007. The study used Lintner's model for data analysis. The core objective of the study was to find the main determinants of the dividend policy of the banks which were listed on the Karachi stock exchange. The data which was already published in the balance sheets were used for the analysis purpose. The study states that banks depend on their current earning while making a decision about the payment of dividends. The study also states that in Pakistan banks which have high profit have more free cash flows and also pay a high dividend.

Amarjit, Nahum and Rajendra (2010), conducted a study in the united states of America. They used two hundred sixty-six (266) financial reports of American service and manufacturing firms. They tried to find out the dividend payout function in the service and manufacturing industry of the USA. The financial data which was submitted by the companies in the form of financial statements to the Security and Exchange

Board of USA was used for the analysis purpose. The study states that payout is a function of debt to equity, sales growth and net profit margin in the Service industry of the USA but in the case of the manufacturing firm of USA payout is the function of profit margin, tax and market to book ratio.

Bogna Kaźmierska (2014) used fourteen (14) different years' data from 2000 to 2012 of Polish companies in Poland. The study used panel techniques for acquiring the desired results. The main theme of the study was to find the determinants of dividend policy of Polish companies in Poland. Already published data were used for analysis purposes. The study tried to find the impact of leverage, profitability, liquidity and size on the dividend payment of the polish firms in the country of Poland. The study concluded that leverage and profitability had a significant but negative relationship with a dividend payout of the firm.

Hafeez Ahmed and Attiya (2012) used six (6) years' data from 2001 to 2006 of three hundred and twenty (320) no financial firms for examining dividend policy determinants and dynamics. Their study was secondary in published because they used already quantitative published data. The empirical finding states that dividend payments of non-financial firms depend on both currents earning per share as well as previous per share dividend. The results state that high dividends are paid by profitable firms with stable earnings. The impact of capital marketization states that firm instead of paying a dividend to their shareholders prefer to invest in their assets.

Aliya Bushra and Nawazish Mirza (2015), tried to identify dividend policy's determinants. They used five years' data from 2005 to 2010 of seventy-five 75 different companies listed on the Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) 100 index of Pakistan. The study was secondary in nature because already published data was used for the acquisition of their desired results. The results of the study state that profitable firms give more dividends than the loss making firms. The private firm gives fewer dividends and omits dividends while the government based firms give more dividends. The results of the study also state that growth in sales has a positive relationship while firm size has a negative relation with dividend yield.

Mark T. Leary and Roni Michaely (2011), conducted research on one thousand three hundred and thirty-five companies for the period from 1985 to 2005. In their sample they had taken those firms which have paid a dividend in at-least 10 different years'. The study concluded that small firms had a smooth dividend policy which had more volatile returns and earnings. They also concluded that companies which had fewer chances of growth and weaker governance had smoother dividend. The study also concluded that firms that had restricted funds and facing agency problems normally had a smoothing dividend.

Belen, Alberto and Julio (2005), conducted a study in Spain on Spanish non-financial quoted companies. They had used the panel data. The main objective of their study was to analyze the dividend policy of those companies. They developed two models. The first model basically explained the conflicts between shareholders and managers of the companies as well as the conflicts between the regulators and shareholders of the company. The second model analyzed how these conflicts affect the dividend policy of a company. The study concluded that regulated firms had a high dividend payout ratio as compare to the no regulated firms.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the detail about the dependent and independent variables, source of data, theoretical framework, population, sample, hypothesis and the techniques which have been used in this study. The overall methodology which has been used for this study is explained in the following.

3.1 Source of Data:

The study is secondary in nature because already published data of electricity producing companies is being used. There are nineteen electricity producing companies listed on Pakistan stock exchange. These nineteen companies which are listed on Pakistan stock exchange and all other non-listed companies which are producing electricity are the population of this study and out of these nineteen companies eight are selected randomly which are the sample of the study. These eight firms have paid a dividend in at-least more than three different years. Financial statements of eight different electricity producing companies have been used for the fourteen years from 2000 to 2013 to derive the expected values. Financial statements of each company have been taken from their official websites. Specifically, from those financial statements income statements, balance sheet and cash flow statements are more important for each company.

3.2 Theoretical framework:

The theoretical framework is normally used to examine the relationship between two variables and the direction of that relationship. In this study dividend policy is the dependent variable whereas the liquidity, profitability, tax, MV to BV, debt to equity and cash flows are the independent variables of the study. The relation between the dependent and independent variables of this study and the direction of that relationship has been shown through the following diagram. Different researchers such as Bogna Kaźmierska (2014), Amarjit, Nahum and Rajendra (2010), Robert King (2015), Abdul Rehman and Takumi (2012), Christopher and Khoury (2014), Eliasu Nuhu (2014), Carlo, Laura and Klaus (2013) have used one or more of these variables to identify the dividend policy of different companies in different countries at different times.

Figure 1: Theoretical framework

3.3 Operational Definition of Variables:

The operational definition of dependent and independent variables of the study and formulas for their estimation is explained in the following.

The dependent variable of the study is dividend policy and it is explained in the following.

3.3.1. Dividend policy:

Dividend policy means the decision of a company whether to pay or not or how much it should pay out of its earning to the shareholders in the form of a dividend. Dividend Policy can be measured by dividend activity, earnings, the ratios of cash dividends to cash flow and sales. Normally for computing dividend policy dividend payout ratio is used whose formula is in the following. To measure dividend policy Dividend Payout ratio is used. (Carlo Cambini, Klaus and Laura 2013).

$$\text{DPOR} = \text{Dividends} / \text{Net Profits}$$

The operational definition of independent variables of this study and formulas for their estimation is explained in the following.

3.3.2. Cash Flows:

Cash flows mean the total amount of money transferred into a business or out of business. (Carlo, Laure and Klaus 2013) Cash flows in this study calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Cash Flows} = \text{Earning after Preferred Dividend} + \text{Depreciation} + \text{Depletion} + \text{Amortization}$$

3.3.3. Debt to Equity:

Debt to Equity shows how much capital is contributed by the owners and creditors of a company. It also indicates the ability of a firm's equity at the time of liquidation to fulfill the company's obligation to creditors. (Amajit Gill and Nahum and Rajendra 2010).The formula of debt to equity is the following:

$$\text{Debt to Equity} = \text{Total Liabilities} / \text{Shareholder's Equity}$$

3.3.4. Liquidity:

liquidity means the ability of a firm to fulfill its short term future obligation. (Franklin and Muthusemy 2010). The most important measure of liquidity is the current ratio. The current ratio is used as a measure of liquidity. The formula of the current ratio is in the following:

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \text{Current Assets} / \text{Current Liabilities}$$

3.3.5. Market to Book Value:

Market to book value basically compares the market value of equity with the book value of equity. (Franklin and Muthusemy 2010) The following formula is used for this purpose:

Market to Book Value = Market Capitalization / Book Value of Equity

Where market capitalization is computed by multiplying the market price of a share with the outstanding share.

3.3.6. Profitability:

Profitability means the ability of a company, firm or business to earn a profit. (Eliasu Nuhu 2014). There are different ratios which are used to calculate the profitability such as return on assets, return on equity and profit margin. In this study profitability is measured using the following formula

Return on asset = EBI&T/ Total Assets

3.3.7. Tax Rate:

The rate is charged by the government on the earning of a company. (Amarjit Gill, Nahum and Rajendra 2010). In this study tax rate is calculated with the help of following formula:

Tax Rate = Corporate Tax / Net Profit before Tax

3.4. Hypothesis:

The hypothesis of the study is as under.

Ho1= There is no significance impact of cash flow on the dividend policy.

Ho2= There is no significance impact of debt to equity on the dividend policy.

Ho3= There is no significance impact of liquidity on the dividend policy.

Ho4= There is no significance impact of the market to book value on the dividend policy.

Ho5= There is no significance impact of profitability on the dividend policy.

Ho6= There is no significance impact of tax on the dividend policy.

Table 1: Correlation

	PAYOUT_RATIO	CASHFLOW	DEBT_TO_EQUITY	LIQUIDITY	MV to BV	PROFITABILITY	TAX
PAYOUT_RATIO	1	0.588023	0.002168	0.055421	0.036948	0.068414	0.136753
CASHFLOW	0.588023	1	-0.204478	0.379891	-0.121849	0.447316	0.334873
DEBT_TO_EQUITY	0.002168	-0.204478	1	-0.512704	-0.119658	-0.242864	-0.186694
LIQUIDITY	0.055421	0.379891	-0.512704	1	0.573047	0.577966	0.373436
MV to BV	0.036948	-0.121849	-0.119658	0.573047	1	0.441087	0.061206
PROFITABILITY	0.068414	0.447316	-0.242864	0.577966	0.441087	1	0.414184
TAX	0.136753	0.334873	-0.186694	0.373436	0.061206	0.414184	1

The value of the correlation between payout ratio and cash flow is 0.588023 which is closer to zero. It means that there is a positive correlation between cash flow and payout ratio and

3.5. Statistical Method:

The dividend policy is computed by using the dividend payout ratio of different electricity companies. Different financial ratios are used for calculating the values of dependent and independent variables. To determine the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable Balanced Panel Regression technique and correlation analysis is used in the study. In the panel regression “Random Effect Method” technique has been used. The same technique has been used by Christopher and Khoury (2014).

Using the ordinary least square method, the following is the regression equation for this study:

Dividend Policy = $\alpha + \beta_1$ (Cash Flow) + β_2 (Debt to Equity) + β_3 (Liquidity) + β_4 (MV to BV) + β_5 (Profitability) + β_6 (Tax)

Where:

Alpha = Constant

Beta = Coefficient of Variable.

MV to BV= Market Value to Book Value.

Results and Analysis

In this part of the study the results of this study are interpreted. In this study two basic techniques are used i.e. Regression and correlation to examine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Correlation Analysis:

Correlation is a tool that is used by the researcher to measure the strength and degree of relationship between the two or more variables. The value of correlation analysis exists between the range from -1 to +1. The number -1 means that there is a very strong negative relationship exists between the variables whereas the number +1 means that there is a very strong positive relationship between the variables. If the value of correlation analysis is 0.00 it means that there is no relationship between the variables.

The correlation between the variables of this study is shown in the following table.

both variables move in a positive direction. The value of the correlation between payout ratio and debt to equity is 0.002168 which is closer to zero. It means that there is a

positive but weak correlation between cash flow and debt to equity and both variables move in a positive direction. The value of the correlation between payout ratio and liquidity is 0.055421 which is closer to zero. It means that there is a positive but weak correlation between payout and liquidity and both variables move in a positive direction. The value of the correlation between payout ratio and market to book value is 0.036948 which is closer to zero. It means that there is a positive but weak correlation between payout and market to book value and both variables move in a positive direction. The value of the correlation between payout ratio and profitability is 0.068414 which is closer to zero. It means that there is a positive but weak correlation between payout and profitability and both variables move in a positive direction. The value of the correlation between payout ratio and tax is 0.136753 which is closer to zero. It means that there is a negative but weak correlation between payout and tax and both variables move in a positive direction.

Regression Analysis:

The most popular statistical technique used for analysis purposes is regression analysis. Regression analysis basically measures the tendency of change in the dependent variable because of the independent variables.

Coefficient: the value of the coefficient basically states how much change is occurred in the dependent variable due to a change in the independent variable of the study.

Standard error: Standard error of variable states that whether such a variable is significant or not. The value of standard error must be less than half of the value of the coefficient for the significance.

Table 2: Regression analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.129427	0.070628	-1.832530	0.0697
CASHFLOW	0.065017	0.005891	11.03594	0.0000
DEBT_TO_EQUITY	0.005683	0.006796	0.836221	0.4049
LIQUIDITY	-0.522229	0.147751	-3.534514	0.0006
MARKET_TO_BOOK_VALUE	0.682502	0.112697	6.056093	0.0000
PROFITABILITY	-0.626424	0.136885	-4.576283	0.0000
TAX	2.637716	1.630344	1.617889	0.1087

The above table is explained in the following in detail.

Constant and Payout Ratio:

The constant coefficient is -0.129427 which means that there is a negative relationship between constant and dividend payout ratio. It means that when all other variables are zero the payout ratio of the firm in the electricity sector will be -0.129427. The value of standard error should be less than half of the value of the coefficient for the significance. The value of standard error is 0.070628 which is not less than half of the coefficient of the constant which shows the insignificance of the constant.

The value of t-statistics must be more than 1.96 or either less than -1.96. The value of t-statistics of constant is more than -1.96 so it is also insignificant.

T-statistic: T-statistic is another tool used to examine the significance of the independent variable in the study. The value of the t-statistic must be greater than 1.96 or it must be less than -1.96 for the significance of variable.

Probability: Probability also representing the significance or insignificance of the variable. For the significance its value must be less than 0.05 or 5%.

R-Square: R- the square is a statistical measure that represents the goodness of fit. It basically represents the degree of change in the dependent variable is predicted due to the independent variable.

F-statistics: t-statistic is used to explain the significance of an independent variable at the individual level, whereas F-statistics is used to explain the significance level of the overall regression model. If the value of F-statistics is greater than 4 then we can predict the model is significant.

Durbin Watson: Durbin Watson is used to explaining the existence of the autocorrelation in the residual from the regression analysis. The value of Durbin Watson is compared to 2, if the value is greater than 2 then we can predict that there is negative autocorrelation in the model, if the value of Durbin Watson is less than 2 there will be positive autocorrelation in the residuals. In this study E-views software has been used for analyzing the data. Because of the panel data Random effect method technique has been used. The results of that test are shown in the table and these results are explaining in the following.

The value of probability should be less than 0.05 which shows the significance of any variable. In this situation the value of the probability of constant is more than 0.05 which also shows the insignificance of the constant.

Cash flow:

The results of the regression state that the relationship between the cash flow of the firm and its payout ratio in the electricity companies of the Pakistan is positive. The results state that if there is lunit change in the value of the cash flow of a company it will bring a change of 0.065017 in the payout ratio of the firm. This change will be in the same direction because of a positive relationship. The standard error of the cash flow's value is 0.005891 which is significant because it is less than half of the value of the coefficient of the cash flow. The t-statistics value of the cash flow is 11.03594 which means that

it is significant because it is more than 1.96. A probability value of the cash flow of the firm is also significant because it is 0.0000 which is less than 0.05.

Debt to Equity:

The result states that there is a positive relationship between the debt to equity and the payout ratio of the electricity companies in Pakistan. It means both moves in the same direction. The value of the coefficient of debt to equity is 0.005683 which means that with 1 unit change in the value of debt to equity the electricity company will change its payout ratio about 0.005683. The standard error of debt to equity is also insignificant because its value is 0.006796 which is more than half of the coefficient of debt to equity ratio. The value of t-statistics of debt to equity ratio is 0.836221, showing the insignificance of debt to equity because it is more than 1.96. A probability value of debt to equity is 0.4049 which is also insignificant because it is more than 0.05.

Liquidity and Payout Ratio:

The liquidity coefficient is -0.522229 which is showing the negative relationship between the liquidity and dividend payout ratio of the electricity firms. It means that with 1 unit positive change in the liquidity of an electricity company there will be -0.522229 change in the dividend payout of the electricity company. The value of the standard error of liquidity is also significant because it is 0.147751 which is less than half of the coefficient of the liquidity. The value of t-statistic is also showing the significance of the liquidity because it is -3.534514 which is less than -1.96. The probability of liquidity is 0.0006 which is less than 0.05 it means it is also significant.

Market to Book Value (MV to BV):

The coefficient of MV to BV is 0.682502 which means that there is a positive relationship between the MV to BV and

Table 3: Weighted statistics

R-squared	0.566106	Mean dependent var	0.165341
Adjusted R-squared	0.541312	S.D. dependent var	0.284833
S.E. of regression	0.192907	Sum squared resid	3.907384
F-statistic	22.83246	Durbin-Watson stat	1.960429
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

R-Square: R-square basically states how much change in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent

dividend payout ratio. The results state that if there is a change of 1 unit in the market to book value it will lead to 0.682502 change in the payout ratio in a positive manner. The standard error of the market to book value is 0.112697 which is also showing the significance of the variable because its value is less than the half of the coefficient of the MV to BV. The value of t-statistics of the market to book value is also significant because its value is more than 1.96 which is 6.056093. Market to book value probability is 0.0000 also significant because it is less than 0.05.

Profitability and Payout Ratio:

The profitability coefficient is -0.626424 which is showing the negative relationship between dividend payout and profitability of the firm. It means that if there is of 1 unit change in the profitability of the firm it will change the payout ratio of the firm by -0.626424. The standard error of the profitability is 0.136885 which is showing the significant of the variable because it is less than half of the coefficient value. T-statistics of the profitability is also significant because it is -4.576283 which is less than -1.96. The probability value is 0.0000 and it is also significant because it is less than 0.05.

Tax and Payout Ratio:

The result states that relationship between Tax and payout ratio is of positive nature because the value of coefficient of tax is 2.637716 which means that if there is change of 1 unit in the amount of tax of electricity companies in Pakistan, the dividend amount will be changed up to 2.637716 and this change will be in the same direction. The standard error of the tax is 1.630344, which is also insignificant because it is not less than half of the value of the coefficient of the tax of electricity companies in Pakistan. The t-statistic is also insignificant because its value is 1.617889 which is less than 1.96. The value of probability is 0.1087 which is also showing the insignificant of the tax because its value is more than 0.05 but at 10% confidence interval it is significant. variable. In this study the value of R-square is 0.566106 which means that almost 57% in this study is explaining the change in the dependent variable. The value or Adjusted R-square is 0.541312 which is almost about 55%. The Adjusted R-square also explains the variation like R-square. Adjusted R-square is more appropriate than R-square and its value is always less than R-square.

F-statistics: F- statistics tell us about the significance of the model overall. The value F-statistic is 22.83246. The value F-test must be greater than 4 for the significance of the model. In this study the value of the F-test is greater than 4 which means that the model of study is significantly expressing the dependent variable.

Durbin Watson: Durban Watson test is used to measure the auto correlation. In this study the Durban Watson test is 1.960429. The value of the Durban Watson test states that there is a positive auto correlation.

On the basis of the results of the study it is concluded that “DEBT_TO_EQUITY” and “TAX” have not a significant impact on the dividend policy of the company. Therefore, the study accepts the null hypothesis Ho2 and Ho6 which is the following.

Ho2= There is no significance impact of Debt to Equity on the dividend policy.

Ho6= There is no significance impact of Tax on the dividend policy.

Whereas result states that cash flow, liquidity, market to book value, profitability, tax, have a significant impact on the dividend policy of the electricity producing companies. Therefore, the study rejects the Ho1, Ho3, Ho4, Ho5.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of the study was to find out factors that influencing dividend policy of electricity producing companies in Pakistan. Therefore, eight electricity producing firms were taken which were listed on the Pakistan stock exchange. The study has used fourteen years' data of these electricity companies from their different balance sheets which were being published by these companies at different times. The variables of the study were Dividend policy, cash flow, debt to equity, liquidity, MV to BV, profitability and tax. Dividend policy was the dependent variable whereas cash flow, debt to equity, liquidity, MV to BV, profitability and tax were the independent variables of the study. The study used a panel random effect method technique to acquire the desired results because the study could not use the fixed effect method.

The result states that there is a significant impact of cash flow on the dividend policy of the electricity companies in Pakistan which confirms the results of Abdul Rehman and Takumi (2012). The results also state that there is a significant impact of liquidity which confirms the result of (Ali Tariq 2015) and Abdul Rehman and Takumi (2012). The result of the study also states that there is a significant impact of profitability which confirms the result of Bahaa Awad (2015), Eliasn Nuhu (2014), Narman Kuzucu (2015) and Ali Tariq (2015). The results of the study also state that there is a significant impact market to book value on the dividend policy of a company which confirms the results of Franklin and Muthusemy (2010). But the results of the study states that there is an insignificant impact of debt to equity which confirms the results of Abdul Rehman and Takumi (2012) and Fazil Haleem and Attiya (2011). The results also state that there is an insignificant impact of tax which confirms the results of Amarjit, Nahum and Rajendra (2010). The results also state that cash flow, debt to equity, MV to BV and tax have a positive relationship with the dividend policy of the companies. But Profitability, and liquidity have a negative relationship with the dividend policy of firms in Pakistan.

It means that in Pakistan liquidity, profit earned by a company, the amount of tax paid by a company to government of Pakistan, market to book value, cash flow of electricity producing companies plays a very vital role while these firms make a decision about the payment of dividend. These all factors influence the company decision that how much amount of dividends should be paid or weather the dividend should be paid or not paid.

5.1. RECOMMENDATIONS:

On the basis of the results of this study there are few recommendations which are in the following.

- 1) Those investors who want to select a dividend paying company while making their investment decision might have to look into the Leverage, liquidity, profitability, firm size, risk, tax, MV to BV, debt to equity, EPS and cash flow of the company. These factors play a very important role in determining the dividend policy of a company.
- 2) The board of directors of electricity producing companies listed at Pakistan stock exchange should give importance to these factors which are mentioned above while deciding the dividend policy of a company. In this way they can make an effective and efficient decision about the payment of dividends. It will also help the company in achieving its main objective of profit maximization and shareholders' satisfaction.

5.2. FUTURE RESEARCH:

The researchers who want to conduct research on electricity companies in Pakistan should try to analyze ownership structure on the dividend policy of those companies. Moreover, they should take more years' data for more effective results. In the future the researchers should try to investigate the generalization of these results beyond the electricity sector as well as Pakistan. Future researchers should also try to analyze the non-linear relationship between the variables.

5.3. LIMITATIONS:

Limitations which were faced during the research conducted are listed below:

1. The sample size was limited due to the availability of the financial data for the last ten years.
2. Due to the barrier of time the researcher was unable to examine the scenario from a broader perspective.
3. On the basis of the sector which was selected, and the study's nature variables used were limited.

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